

CoSTAR User Persona Interviews Report

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Abstract

Convergent Screen Technologies and performance in Realtime (CoSTAR) is a £75.6 million investment by the UKRI Infrastructure Fund, delivered by the Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC). It creates a national network of research and development (R&D) labs built to maintain the UK's world-leading position in the development and exploitation of creative IP. The CoSTAR Network offers world-leading facilities, technology research, and a range of academic and industry partnerships to support the continued growth of our gaming, TV, film, performance, and digital entertainment sectors.

This report maps the CoSTAR creative technology R&D ecosystem based on stakeholder interviews, emphasising the importance of understanding users as a foundation for effective service design. Interviews with representatives across the CoSTAR labs, involving Realtime, National and Live Lab, were conducted in the period of April-May 2025. The thematic analysis of the interview transcripts resulted in the creation of seven personas that engage with the CoSTAR network: five of them are user personas as followed: 1) *The Production-Led Innovator* captures the main user type of CoSTAR that blends creativity, technology, and commercial desires; 2) *The Cultural Experimenter* focuses on the capabilities of creative technology for audience experience; 3) *The Pipeline Builder* build tools that shape the creative production pipelines; 4) *The Platform Pioneer* fosters early-stage validation by enabling diverse real-world scenarios; 5) *The Grassroot Catalyst* is the fertiliser layer of the ecosystem. The last two of them are affiliated personas are as follows: 6) *The Enabler* sustains the creative technology ecosystem by providing the financial, strategic, and structural conditions; 7) *The Researcher* finds innovative connections with their expertise to explore the capabilities of creative technology.

These user personas provide a prerequisite layer for designing coherent user journeys, identifying touchpoints, and aligning services both across different CoSTAR network labs and across creative, technical, and institutional partners. This research positions user understanding not as an afterthought but as a strategic design method essential for shaping CoSTAR R&D ecosystems that are empathetic, inclusive, and capable of translating creative and technological value into stakeholder journeys across the network.

1. Current Context

Context of the Study

In a CoSTAR Network Board meeting (February 2025), the need for a better understanding of the attributes of CoSTAR users was raised to facilitate their engagement with the CoSTAR network. This realisation started the conversations around bringing user research staff together to work towards defining and clarifying the CoSTAR users in the form of personas, which would then serve to create potential user/customer journeys through the CoSTAR network, resulting in an efficient user experience for those users. In addition, the persona attributes would also provide a framework for CoSTAR stakeholders to recognise at which point, and how, they can support these users.

Aim / Objectives

The wider aim of the project was to explore how CoSTAR can support the user/customer touchpoints across its network, and ensure that the experience of the user/customers is consistent and efficient.

The objectives were to:

1. gather views from CoSTAR stakeholders to inform the development of customer personas (evidence-based representation of typical CoSTAR users)
2. prepare the groundwork for mapping the journey of these personas across the network

Corresponding research questions are:

Who are CoSTAR users/customers/partners?

What are their goals, motivations, and challenges when engaging with CoSTAR?

What is the scope for manoeuvring the CoSTAR network for different users?

Network Labs Involvements

This project has been a collaborative effort between the Realtime Lab and National Lab, alongside some contributions from the Foresight Lab. Involved in initial discussions were Ecem Ince, Hazel Dixon, Andrea Szymkowiak, Gregor White, Frauke Zeller, and Billy Franks. The collaboration involved online monthly (between March-August 2025) meetings and idea exchanges. The subsequent study involved collaborative designing of study material, collecting and analysing data (starting spring 2025). The main team members involved in conducting this study were:

Ecem Ince (Realtime Lab, Abertay University)

Hazel Dixon (National Lab, Royal Holloway)

Andrea Szymkowiak (Realtime Lab, Abertay University)

2. Methodology

Data Collection Approach

We employed a qualitative research approach using semi-structured online interviews because this study seeks to understand the depth, complexity, and subjectivity of user experiences. Qualitative methods enable the generation of rich, interpretive data that capture the affective and contextual dimensions of user experiences (Hammarberg et al. 2016); hence, this method aligns with our focus on revealing stakeholder motivations, goals, and pain points when engaging with CoSTAR.

The interview data were used to create User Personas to clarify what the CoSTAR Network is for, to build empathy, to support scenario building, and guide decision-making (Nielsen 2013) for the operational team to support users manoeuvring CoSTAR.

Participants

This research consisted of two tracks of research:

1. Five interviews with CoSTAR Lab or R&D Program Directors
2. Five interviews with disabled individuals working in the creative R&D space

We interviewed seven CoSTAR Lab or R&D program directors (the 'Participants') from three labs (Realtime, Live, National), four of them identified as female, three of them identified as male. In total, five interviews were conducted, with two out of five involving two Participants at the same time, while the remaining interviews involved one Participant only. Interviews took place between April 15th and May 27th 2025.

As a parallel track, we sought to understand the experiences that disabled users of our R&D labs might have. Through our lab connections, we recruited 5 creatives who have previously applied for R&D innovation funds for a 60-minute interview and compensated them with £25 Love2Shop vouchers. These Participants had a mixture of disabilities (1x visual impairment, 2x neurodiversity, 2x brain injury causing neurological and mobility impairments). These Participants were interviewed using questions specifically on EDI aspects and analysed using relevant codes and themes. The findings are presented in a separate report (see [Title](#) Hazel Dixon). Hence, this report presents the process and findings of the five interviews with CoSTAR Lab or R&D Program Directors.

Materials: Questionnaire

When we constructed the interview questionnaire, we identified the central, general components of a user persona relevant to the project's context, such as user goals, motivations, pain points, and expectations, ensuring that each question encouraged Participants to reflect on the potential user's mindsets. The users/customers of CoSTAR were described as typical companies and organisations instead of individuals. Aligned with the components, we explored Participants' perceptions regarding *User base*, *Technology-adaptiveness*, *Motivational drivers*, *User Segmentation*, and *Engagement*. The questionnaire involved 16 questions in total (see *Appendix I*). In addition, deeper probing questions explored the following categories: Context, Application process, R&D process itself, Accessibility (see *Appendix II*).

The study presented here will focus on the interviews with CoSTAR Lab or R&D Program Directors

Study Procedure: Online

For recruitment, CoSTAR stakeholders were provided with the context of the need for this study and invited via email to take part.

We started the interview with a *Warm-up* activity aimed at exploring the perceived distinct roles and contributions of each lab taking part before posing the interview questions. Each interview was conducted over a video conferencing platform (Teams), lasting between 60 - 90 minutes. The study was conducted under an umbrella ethical approval (Abertay University) involving CoSTAR stakeholders.

Data Collection and Analysis

The interviews were audio recorded within a Teams platform and then transcribed into text form by using Teams' auto-transcription option. After the automatic transcription process, each interview transcript was proofread and corrected to eliminate mistakes generated by the automatic transcript generation. All original recordings were deleted after they had been transcribed.

We employed thematic analysis (TA) when analysing the qualitative data, due to its nature to extract complex, nuanced and rich findings (Braun and Clarke 2006). TA allows identifying, analysing and reporting patterns within data, while organising and describing the data set in rich detail. The steps for TA are as follows: 1) familiarising yourself with the data, 2) generating initial codes, 3) searching for themes, 4) reviewing themes, 5) defining and naming themes, and 6) writing the report.

Since our aim was to understand and categorise the Participants' perceived user personas, and the questions were specifically constructed with that aim, this analysis is using deductive TA, where we expect the themes identified will bear high relation to the questions that were asked of the Participants, consistent with the pre-determined categorises that define 'User Persona'.

All data were analysed using NVivo, a software package for systematic qualitative data analysis. We first familiarised ourselves with the data by reading through all transcripts several times, noting key expressions that reflected both the potential user categories and users' attitudes and needs. Then, the initial codes were assigned to the statements. After coding the interview transcripts, responses were clustered into wider categories, which were then visualised. An example is shown overleaf in Fig.1.

Fig.1 shows that the clustering was transparent due to the deductive analysis process. The overarching interview questions led for clusters to appear, but this was not a restricting factor. Some clusters appeared by looking through the data and identifying interrelations. Similarly, not all questions strictly turned into a cluster. While the thematic clusters initially reflected the structure of the interview guide, the relationship between user categories and their specific experiences was not always directly linked. The question "What kind of customers will you encounter?" prompted Participants to establish preliminary categories, but the follow-up responses often revealed more general reflections of users rather than relating reflections to specific user categories. This necessitates further interpretive work to trace possible connections and overlaps across response components. Hence, we undertook a dual analysis process. This dual categorisation was necessary to process responses consistent with the pre-existing themes (e.g., user types) and to generate interpretive insights that go beyond the pre-existing themes to emerging themes based on the comprehensiveness of data. Here, we focused specifically on 'user types' in a second-level analysis because they strongly informed the development of the persona categories themselves, while the other themes functioned more as features of those personas. This dual analysis process is summarised as follows:

1. In the first-level analysis, the structural themes were reflected from the question sequence and aligned well with the questions themselves (e.g., types of customers, goals, pain points) (see Appendix III).

- In the second-level analysis, the category “Customer/User types” was specifically prioritised as a central category (as personas)(Appendix IV) from which to establish cross-cutting relationships with other categories.

Fig. 1: Illustrative example of the Thematic Analysis method, from raw quotes to codes to themes.

Intra-rater reliability is a process that measures the consistency of a single researcher when coding data from the same subject under the same conditions at different times. This process is carried out to increase the validity and trustworthiness of the research results. The results are compared between Time 1 (June 15th - July 30th 2025) and Time 2, (November 17th - 30th 2025). During the intra-rater reliability calculation, the ‘unit’ is defined as a meaningful segment, which may include a sentence or a couple of sentences, around an idea. Approximately 30% of the units from each interview have been sampled to recode (55 out of 184).

The codes from Time 1 and 2 were compared, and percentage agreement was used to assess intra-rater consistency by comparing researcher decisions in Time 1 and 2 as the number of agreements divided by total coding decisions (x100) (McHugh 2012). The result is 92% (51 out of 55), indicating a reasonable level of intra-rater consistency.

Self-reflexivity statement

In line with best practice, included here is the researcher's statement for the coding of data, as qualitative data analysis is, by definition, subjective, though biases should be avoided. As a CoSTAR researcher, I acknowledge that my own background and experiences have shaped the way I approach this study. My existing knowledge of being in a CoSTAR ecosystem and being exposed to the early CoSTAR context may influence what I notice, the kinds of questions I ask, and how I interpret the data. My aim is not to remove my influence, but to make it visible and accounted for within the analysis. Linking quotes with the creation of codes with subsequent theme identification should make this process transparent (see Appendix II and III).

3. CoSTAR User Personas

Based on the identified codes and themes, 7 User Personas were created. Table 1 provides an overview of each User Persona with descriptions of typical attributes. Each User Persona is further outlined below with illustrative quotes and characteristics. The reader should be reminded that the created personas do not correspond to a particular individual or organisation but represent the user types. We grouped personas into 2 major categories: User Personas and Affiliated Personas. User Personas are typical users of CoSTAR services, which require targeted engagement efforts, while Affiliated Personas are not typical users but are naturally existing within the CoSTAR system and play an important role for CoSTAR. The latter category arose from the coding of material and was not initially anticipated.

Table 1: Overview of User Personas and Affiliated Personas with descriptions of typical attributes

User Personas	Production-Led Innovator	Small-to-medium creative technology companies that are production-driven and commercially oriented, balancing artistic innovation with client-ready deliverables.
	Cultural Experimenter	Creative organisations such as museums or theatres that explore emerging technologies to deepen audience engagement and artistic experience.
	Pipeline Builder	Tech-led SMEs that design and build tools, software, and systems enabling creative production pipelines across the wider industry.
	Technological Pioneer	Large technology firms are conducting early-stage R&D and user testing to explore how new technologies will be experienced and adopted in real-world scenarios.
	Grassroot Catalyst	Community-based creative groups that are technology enthusiasts bringing diversity and social value at the ecosystem’s foundation.
Affiliated Personas	Strategic Funder	Funding and policy bodies that shape the ecosystem by providing resources, frameworks, and legitimacy for creative and technological experimentation.
	Researcher-Innovator	Hybrid academic and creative practitioners who translate and link knowledge with technological experimentation and reflection.

The User Persona descriptions outlined below describe the main attributes, characteristics, goals, pains, and needs of the Personas. They also contain our interpretations of the considerations and the impact of the personas in relation to CoSTAR (why the Personas are relevant to CoSTAR), accompanied by illustrative quotes and images¹.

¹ The user persona images were developed with the assistance of Gemini’s Nano Banana, while the information was guided and reviewed by the authors.

User Personas

User Persona 1: The Production-Led Innovator

Creative innovation

Blending art & tech

Market-ready products

Bridging the gaps in-between disciplines

"Balancing creativity, technology and market-readiness"

Who is it?

Small-to-medium creative technology companies that are *production-led* working at the intersection of art, technology, and commercial interest, focusing on delivery pipelines and user-oriented creative work. These companies are embedded within the creative industries and often serve as the practical bridge between conceptual design, production and market application. They are keen to experiment with new technology and explore innovative solutions to specific problems they are facing.

Risk & Opportunity Space: Bridging the gap between disciplines | Working on the exclusion risk | Disruptive changes in the industry

Persona Characteristics

- **Areas:** Live entertainment, Film, Game, Immersive (varies)
- **Company Scale:** Small-Medium
- **Team:** Creative technologists, production designers, technicians, artists...
- **Technology Adaptiveness:** Most users are anticipated to have medium-to-high technological literacy, though even tech-literate users may lack familiarity with VP tech. Creative users within this persona type also tend to express heightened nervousness about AI.
- **Risk-Appetite:** High

Goals

- Deliver market-ready products or services, business growth, revenue and award
- Gaining a novel way of thinking and strategic knowledge

Pains

- Particular technical and creative problems to solve, which require infrastructure & staff
- Managing IP
- Lack of guidance on how they will develop products/services
- Lack of guidance on how they will be involved in CoSTAR

Needs

- Need admin guidance in the application & involvement process, and help with managing IP
- Opportunities to experiment safely and navigating time as a running business

Derived Considerations & Impact

- ★ This persona captures the key user type of CoSTAR.
 - ★ Their significance lies in companies being simultaneously creative and commercial.
 - ★ Have the potential to be categorised into two sub-groups: early-phase vs market-ready
- ? How can we utilise an environment where individual companies gain benefits while creating a sustainable impact that applies to the wider sector?

Quotes

"We're going to have people with that kind of production to market front end, which is the specification of the network labs, is to work with companies at that later stage, TRL, close to market, and I guess they'll be our primary customers" (P1).

"Our customers would be creative industries companies with particular production challenges" (P3).

User Persona 2: The Cultural Experimenter

Audience
innovation

Live
Experiences

Socially
motivated

Cultural
Heritage

“Cultural innovation through audiences”

Who is it?

This persona represents creative organisations such as museums, galleries, theatres, visitor attractions, and other cultural venues that operate within the creative industries but with *non-commercial or less-commercial motivations*. They are production-led in practice, like creating exhibitions, performances, experiences but are guided by audience engagement, artistic experimentation, and social value rather than direct market profit.

Risk & Opportunity Space: Bridging the gap between disciplines | Translating technology innovation to stories and experiences | Working on the exclusion risk

Persona Characteristics

- **Areas:** Galleries, Libraries, Theatres, Visitor attractions, Live experiences
- **Company Scale:** Small-Medium
- **Team:** Creative producers, curators, designers, public engagement team
- **Technology Adaptiveness:** Higher nervousness about AI, tech reservation is apparent. They are keen to explore new tools to enhance engagement, but not so technology-literate.
- **Risk-Appetite:** High

Goals

- Enhancing audience engagement and discovering new creative possibilities with new tech
- Gaining knowledge and new ways of looking

Pains

- Lack of technical capability
- Managing IP

Needs

- Infrastructure and staff access
- Help with managing IP
- Help in navigating and finding time as a running business

Derived Considerations & Impact

- ★ They have direct access to audiences for testing new experiences publicly
- ★ Are motivated by cultural relevance, provide rich and contextual challenges

? How can we enable sector-wide generalisable audience innovation starting from contextual challenges?

Quotes

"End goal is larger audiences" (P5)

"We will have less commercial organizations that can bring problems to us from a kind of slightly different place, which are people have an audience, so museums, galleries, events, visitor attractions, things like that, who might be able to use this technology" (P1).

User Persona 3: Pipeline Builder

Technological
innovation

Pipeline
Improvements

Workflow
Optimisation

Tools - making

“Building the tools that shape creative production”

Who is it?

This persona represents tech-led SME companies that focus on developing tools, platforms, and software systems that support creative technology workflows. They focus on building and improving the infrastructure such as toolkits, plug-ins, and frameworks, that enable others in the creative industry to produce efficiently, collaboratively, and at scale. This user group is highly technical, but their purpose is artistic enablement: creating systems that empower/enable creativity.

Risk & Opportunity Space: Bridging the gap between disciplines | Working on the exclusion risk

Persona Characteristics

- **Areas:** Software, Hardware development
- **Company Scale:** Small-Medium
- **Team:** Engineers, creative technologists, software developers, makers, designers...
- **Technology Adaptiveness:** High technology-literacy and knowledge
- **IP Familiarity:** Variable

Goals

- Building the tools that shape creative /virtual production
- Pipeline and system improvements

Pains

- Lack of IP familiarity
- Struggles with inclusivity issues due to the required technical literacy level

Needs

- Infrastructure & staff access, and different contexts to test tools
- Help with managing IP

Derived Considerations & Impact

- ★ The outputs have the potential to scale across sectors, hence be scalable, adaptable, and transferable
- ★ This persona type requires attention to avoid potential exclusivity issues due to high technical necessity
- ? How can we diversify and expand funding opportunities to also involve people who are not high-technology-literacy?

Quotes

“There will be creative technologists, and technologists who are looking to build tools to fit into that pipeline and workflow and may need access to our expertise in software development and problem solving.(P1)”

User Persona 4: The Platform Pioneers

Innovation
leaders

Early-phase
testing

Validating
innovation

“Testing futures through early-stage innovation”

Who is it?

This persona represents large, tech-led, mostly service-based companies, often established industry leaders that engage in early-stage research and development to explore new innovations and use scenarios. They use partnerships with creative organisations, research labs, and end-users to test tools, gather user insights, and forecast technological relevance.

Risk & Opportunity Space: Disruptive changes in the industry

Persona Characteristics

- **Areas:** Communication, Network, Software & Hardware development...
- **Company Scale:** Large
- **Team:** (Large-scale) Executives, Service & Operational team, Engineers, Marketing...
- **Technology Adaptiveness:** High
- **IP Familiarity:** Medium to High

Goals

- Access a diverse audience and understand real-world use scenarios
- Foster early-stage validation

Pains:

- Limited access to creative R&D environments with use-cases
- Lack of context to predict early-phase user insights

Needs

- Access to variety of use cases to gather user insights
- Low-risk prototyping opportunities
- Structured collaboration instead of experimenting

Derived Considerations & Impact

- ★ Early-stage R&D benefits to translate technical potential to meaningful user insights
- ★ Important consideration here is the diverse and repetitive use cases for validation
- ? How can we utilise the need for use cases in this persona through productive connection building within CoSTAR and creative technology ecosystem?

Quotes

“They would access the technology to be able to test their tools and processes that they're developing.(P5)”

“They want to know how the end users are going to use those technologies.(P5)”

“They say: there's this cool technology — how is it going to be used by the end user?(P3)”

User Persona 5: The Grassroot Catalyst

Ecosystem - building

Cultural fertility

Experimentation

Inclusion

“Innovation from the margins, connection from the ground up.”

Who is it?

This persona represents grassroots and community-driven, enthusiastic, creative organisations, informal networks, collectives, and small-scale creative initiatives that often fall outside institutional KPIs but are essential to the cultural and creative ecosystem. These include grassroots music venues, women-led and BAME creative organisations, and local creative communities. They act as incubators of diversity, inclusion, storytelling, and innovation.

Risk & Opportunity Space: Ecosystem Building | Translating technology innovation to stories and experiences | Working on the exclusion risk

Persona Characteristics

- **Areas:** Live entertainment, Film, Game, Immersive (varies)
- **Scale /Orientation** Small (e.g. BAME-led labs, DIY community spaces, grassroots music venues, women or LGBT-led filmmaking collectives)
- **Technology Adaptiveness:** Low. Mostly technology-reserved and illiterate.
- **IP Familiarity:** Low to Medium
- **Risk appetite:** Risk-Seeking

Goals

- Tell their stories and represent their communities
- De-risking the creative experiments and tests as running a full-time organisation, without heavy constraints
- Access tools they normally wouldn't be financially able to

Pains:

- Lack of knowledge about the technology and feeling intimidated to be “not technical enough”
- Being technologically-reserved, potentially afraid to explore new possibilities.
- Unclear pathways into R&D networks & unclear on how CoSTAR can help

Needs

- New and clearer forms of engagement
- Lower-barrier and entry points for confidence-building (e.g. test sessions, simple walkthroughs)
- Opportunities to experiment safely (e.g. creative jams, informal prototypes or demos)
- Reach and knowledge-sharing that will help ecosystem building

Derived Considerations & Impact

- ★ They represent the fertiliser layer of the ecosystem
- ★ An essential source of cultural renewal, social inclusion, and EDI (Equity, Diversity, Inclusion)
- ? How can we create clear and context-rooted pathways that encourage this persona to develop an expansive mindset capable of producing effective value to wider sector?

Quotes

“The innovation creative practice that happens much closer to the grassroots, and tends to be responsive to circumstances, and to individual challenges.”(P3)

“And that access extends beyond just SMEs. Within diversity to those that haven't got access to that technology, BAME companies”(P4)

Affiliated Personas

The Enabler

This persona represents funding and policy bodies, organisations that sustain the creative technology ecosystem by providing the financial, strategic, and structural conditions that enable experimentation, collaboration, and growth.

The Researcher

This persona represents individual or group of researchers, creative technologists, and innovation leads who work across academia, industry, and the arts, who find innovative connections between their work and the potential of CoSTAR and want to experiment with tools.

4. Discussion Points

Across all CoSTAR personas, a recurring pattern is creativity, technology, innovation and infrastructure. No single user persona operates in isolation, and each represents a different entry point into a shared CoSTAR ecosystem of innovation. Across the ecosystem, users differ in their relationship to creativity, technology, and risk. Production-Led Innovators favour workflow stability and deliverability; Cultural Experimenters prioritise audience impact; Pipeline Builders focus on solving technical problems and generalisability; Platform Pioneers prioritise testing future use cases; and Grassroot Catalyst highlights representation, community, and stories.

This diversity of users can be interpreted as a condition that demands creative bridging and non-linear thinking rather than uniformity and simplification. It also emphasises the need for considering each persona's need for different entry points into the CoSTAR journey, which requires for CoSTAR to be modular and adaptive, as well as allowing for multiple modes of participating and engagement.

Tensions in the CoSTAR Ecosystem

The creation of CoSTAR User Personas reveals various tensions in manoeuvring the CoSTAR network:

Production-led vs Technology-led Personas reveal how creative technology ecosystems are built on complementary drives: one prioritising content and expression, the other tools and systems. The shared goal is to create R&D and improve systems and the creative industry.

User Personas vs Affiliated Personas form a pattern of support sustaining the ecosystem and reflects the differences in required effort for engagement and marketing for different agents being involved in CoSTAR.

Commercial vs Experimental reflects the tension between market-oriented functionality and exploratory intentions within the ecosystem. On one side, commercially oriented users prioritise scalability, deliverability, and measurable outcomes. On the other, experimentally oriented users prioritise open-ended discovery, and artistic risk. This is also mentioned in parallel to industry-academy divide throughout the data.

An important way to think about these tensions in an effective way could be to think about them as a dynamic space, rather than binary oppositions. These tensions could be considered as drivers of dynamism as they can create the friction through which adaptation and negotiation occur within the ecosystem. A good query here would be: How can we navigate or transform these tensions into productive opportunity areas that can most benefit CoSTAR?

Designing Empathy into the System

User empathy extends beyond individuals to organisational mindset shift. It is about how CoSTAR understand users' constraints and languages. Our analysis of the interviews highlights the way how CoSTAR could start considering the different needs of users and motivations. For example, grassroots and community actors need access and confidence that they can engage with CoSTAR; SMEs need clarity and applicable support; Researchers and Enablers need evidence and accountability. Bridging this empathy requires constant communication, transparency and contextual user research. This may also create the foundation to create framework for designing effective touchpoints within CoSTAR.

Inclusion as Critical and Urgent Necessity

One of the common and insistent emphases during the interviews was that grassroots work is not on the margins; instead it is an important aspect of the CoSTAR R&D network. The Grassroot Catalyst persona, like small music venues, women-led or BAME collectives, and local creative spaces, make things up as they go, testing ideas before they are even called innovation. Besides, next-generation young creators under 30, people with creative minds but not necessarily technical, are the ones CoSTAR may need to consider. They show what inclusion and experimentation really look like when there is no funding brief or institutional framework shaping it. To treat grassroots work as a systemic necessity is to build an ecosystem that lets new stories, tools, and ways of working rise from the ground.

This consideration highlights an enquiry: "How to redefine and expand our R&D parameters to work with those who face barriers, to avoid facing the risk of solely working with big companies that already do R&D?"

Seeking value in balancing the contextual and generalisable benefit

Users come to the CoSTAR R&D network, with a variety of challenges. The potential impact of the solutions for these challenges varies depending on the extent of the impact. Some users come with a particular technological or creative challenge, and CoSTAR solutions may benefit solely them as it may be a very particular challenge, specific to their context, or to a small group of other businesses that operate in this realm. On the other hand, there might be problems that appear from a particular context, but the solutions may impact the creative technology industry on a wider scale. One significant challenge to tackle here is, as it is emphasised during the interviews, that industry-wide innovations often comes bigger players, which may risk ignoring the smaller companies with great potential.

CoSTAR network values the solution-creating mindset which cares about the individual benefit, yet which goes beyond individual benefits, and provides a knowledge wider into the sector and creative economy that could be build upon, either technically, creatively or methodologically. Hence the enquiry could be "How can we create impact regardless the size and commerciality of the user, but the innovative potential?"

5. Implications & Future Scenarios: Customer Journey Map

This research develops a User Persona-based framework for understanding the creative technology R&D ecosystem, positioning user insight as a core driver of effective creative R&D systems and service design.

Through qualitative interviews and thematic analysis, seven User Personas were identified which can be characterised as creative producers, technologists, funders, researchers, and grassroots communities. Each Persona captures distinct motivations, capacities, and relationships with CoSTAR. By grounding CoSTAR engagements in user understanding, this research provides a foundation for Customer Journey Mapping (CJM), enabling clearer identification of needs, barriers, and touchpoints across the ecosystem with the aim to support the user in that journey. Affiliated Personas are of relevance to CoSTAR through their continuous interactions with CoSTAR stakeholders themselves as well as user types.

Beyond their usefulness for identifying and guiding CJM, the personas serve as strategic design tools as they have potential to g communication, partnership models, evaluation criteria, and long-term engagement strategies. The findings of this study thus feed directly towards the second aim of this work, prepare the

groundwork for mapping the journey of these personas across the network, which is to be explored in the subsequent phase with CoSTAR stakeholders.

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Appendix I: User Personas Interview Questionnaire

Warm-up

- 1) How does your Lab fit in the CoSTAR network? What is your Lab's unique contribution?
- 2) Why are the customers interested in you over your competitors? / What do you offer that differentiates you from other providers offering similar services?

User base

- 3) What kind of customers will you encounter?
- 4) What industries or sectors do your customers primarily operate in?
- 5) What type/size of organizations are your customers (e.g., startups, SMEs, large enterprises, individual creatives, government-related, nonprofits)?

Technology-adaptiveness

- 6) What technologies /tools/infrastructures do your customers typically use?
- 7) What is their general level of technology-adaptiveness (*or technology maturity*) level (e.g., early adopters, cautious adopters, laggards)?

Motivational drivers

- 8) Are there particular triggers/circumstances that lead users to approach you? /OR/ What are the main challenges /pain points your customers face before coming to you?
- 9) What are the primary goals/end goals your users/customers are trying to achieve with your product/service?
- 10) What kind of solid outcomes/deliverables do your users want to achieve?

User differentiation

- 11) What are your criteria for engaging with customers? What are the key points /ways in which your user segments differ from one another?
- 12) Do you have the ideal customer profiles you target more than others?
- 13) Do you have any personas or customer archetypes already defined? If so, can you share them? Are there any particular examples /case studies that show your users and what they achieve with your service?
- 14) (bonus) What have you learned about your customers that surprised you?

Engagement

- 15) How do your customers typically approach/interact with your Lab?

DEI considerations

- 16) What barriers do your customers encounter in accessing your spaces or programs? These could be physical but also social/cultural/mental etc.

Appendix II: First-Level Analysis Results

Codes	Themes	Description
Production creative-led & commercial	User types	Distinct themes of potential companies and people who will interact with, benefit from, or be affected by CoSTAR
Production creative-led & audience		
Tech-led service-based		
Tech-led build tools		
Grassroot and community		
Researchers & Innovators		
Stakeholders & Funders		
Bridging the gap between disciplines	R&D risk and opportunity space	
Exclusion risks		

Translating to stories		The overall landscape of what could go wrong and can be turned into an advantage
Disruptive changes in the industry		
De-risking the tests	User Takeaway Opportunities	What users can gain, learn, or experience from engaging with CoSTAR
Access to network		
Support for engaging with <i>new ways of working</i>		
Access to infrastructure and staff		
High service-led capacity		
User focused research		
Deliver market-ready service and products		
Infrastructure and staff access		
Finding time as a running business		
IP management		
Lack of guidance		
Particular challenge, generalisable outcome	Type of Challenge	The nature of the difficulty being addressed in the CoSTAR R&D
Particular challenge, individual outcome		
Particular challenge, unknown solution		
No particular challenge, experimentation		
Pipeline improvements	Goals & Expected Outcomes	The intended final state or achievement of CoSTAR
Business growth and revenue		
Larger audiences		
Research and new knowledge		
Tech-illiterate	Technology Adaptiveness	How well users can adjust to, integrate, or evolve with emerging technologies of CoSTAR
Tech-literate		
Tech-reserved		
High IP familiarity	IP Familiarity	The degree to which the team understands and manages intellectual property
Low IP familiarity		
Risk-seeking	Risk Appetite	The degree of uncertainty or potential loss that a team or organization is willing to
Risk-averse		

		tolerate in pursuit of innovation
Unclear of usefulness	Barrier to entry	The difficulty that prevents new users, competitors, or collaborators from easily participating or reproducing CoSTAR
Technology knowledge		
Financial challenges		
Administrative complexity		
Physical access and location		
Social accessibility		
Innovation and creative IP	Value and impact	The overall significance and contribution of users' activities with CoSTAR
Generalisability (value beyond creativity)		
Ecosystem building and social impact		
Accessibility and Inclusivity		
Making use of infrastructure		
What CoSTAR is not	CoSTAR Defining	Refers to defining the project through the CoSTAR framework
Aim of the lab		
Lab differentiator		

Appendix III: Second-Level Analysis Results

Production-Led Innovator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 > Bridging the gap between disciplines 1 > Exclusion risks 2 > Deliver market-ready products & services 2 > De-risking the test 5 > Pipeline improvements 6 > Technology-literate 6 > Technology-reserved 7 > High IP-familiarity
Cultural Experimenter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 > Exclusion risks 4 > No particular challenge, experimentation 5 > Pipeline improvements 6 > Technology-reserved 7 > High IP-familiarity 8 > Risk-seeking
Pipeline Builder	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 > Bridging the gap between disciplines 1 > Exclusion risks 2 > Deliver market-ready products & services 2 > De-risking the test 5 > Pipeline improvements 7 > Low IP-familiarity
Technological Pioneer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 > Exclusion risks 2 > De-risking the test 7 > Low IP-familiarity

	8 > Risk-averse
Grassroot Catalyst	1 > Translating to stories 2 > De-risking the test 4 > No particular challenge, experimentation 6 > Technology-reserved 6 > Technology-illiterate 7 > High IP-familiarity 8 > Risk-seeking 10 > Ecosystem building and social impact
Enabler	N/A
Researcher	4 > No particular challenge, experimentation 9 > Administrative complexity